

Interply Friction Characterization of Continuous and Stretch Broken Carbon Fiber (SBCF) Composites during Forming

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Outline

- Challenges in composite forming
- Introduction to stretch broken carbon fiber (SBCF)
- Relevance of friction during forming
- Interply friction characterization
 - Test materials
 - Test method
 - Test matrix
- Results and discussion
- Future work and conclusion

Challenges during Composite Forming

- Conventional CFRP composites made of continuous fibers –
 - high axial stiffness
 - low strain-to-failure
- Poor drapability and limited formability over double-curved or complex geometries
- Leads to forming defects: wrinkling, buckling, bridging, misalignment
- Limits large-scale adoption of CFRPs as replacement for metals in aerospace structures

Forming defects : (a,b) Ply wrinkling and fiber buckling (c) Bridging

Stretch Broken Carbon Fiber (SBCF)

Metal-like formability in carbon fiber composites without compromising stiffness or strength

Stretch Broken Carbon Fiber (SBCF)

- Discontinuous, aligned short fibers with variable lengths (1- 40 mm)
- Continuous carbon fiber tows broken in tension, with breaks occurring at natural flaws
- Forming facilitated by axial stretching of the fibers when impregnated with resin (pseudo-ductility)
- Tensile strength retained through local shear load transfer

Relevance of Friction during Composite Forming

- Interply shear and slippage are essential deformation mechanisms for forming laminates into complex geometries
- Slippage is governed by interply friction, involves relative movement between adjacent uncured plies
- High frictional resistance limits interply shear, leading to forming defects
- SBCF introduces stretch deformation mode, reduces influence of friction and shear

Interply Friction Characterization: Materials

Two carbon/epoxy prepregs :

- **Stretch broken carbon fiber (SBCF) prepregs**

- MSU Hexcel IM7 SBCF fibers impregnated with CYCOM[®] 977-3 resin in collaboration with USM (RC=37.5 %, FAW=139.6 gsm, Water Pickup (%) = 0.53)

- **Continuous carbon fiber (CCF) prepregs** –

- Syensqo Hexcel 12k IM7 continuous fiber impregnated with CYCOM[®] 977-3 resin (RC = 32.7, FAW= 137.9 gsm, Water Pickup (%) = 0.57)

Novel stretch-breaking process developed at MSU

Interply Friction Characterization: Pull-through Test Method

Test configuration and test matrix

	Clamping block	Central specimen	Clamping block
SBCF test	0° CCF	$[0]_{12}$ =All 0° SBCFs	0° CCF
CCF test	0° CCF	$[0]_{12}$ =All 0° CCFs	0° CCF

Test *	Temperature (°C)	Normal pressure (MPa)	Pulling rate (mm/min)
1	121	0.1	1
2	121	0.3	1
3	121	0.6	1

*Each test corresponds to three replicates and results are averaged for three tested samples

Results : CCF vs SBCF

Load due to frictional resistance increases with displacement and normal pressure

Load relaxation for each test after frictional resistance reached a threshold value

Results: continued

Results: continued

Shear stress, $\tau = F/A$

F = max load from load displacement curve (in N)

A = area = $(w * l) * 2 = 3386 \text{ mm}^2$

Conclusion

- Differences in the material deformation behavior between CCF and SBCF laminates during interply friction testing -
 - For CCF laminates -
 - primarily frictional interply shear, higher normal pressure increases resistance
 - For SBCF laminates -
 - axial stretching at the onset of high interply frictional resistance
- Unique SBCF deformation behavior can help mitigate excessive shear stress generation

Future work

- Continue testing to study effect of temperature and ply orientation
- Determine threshold between stretch and slippage response under various forming conditions

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Thank you

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